

NEW DATA ON DOLICHOPODIDAE (DIPTERA) FROM KAZAKHSTAN AND KYRGYZSTAN

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Negrobov O.P. & Grichanov I.Ya. New data on Dolichopodidae (Diptera) from Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan. Summary. The faunistic data of the results of collecting dolichopodids (8 species) in different regions of Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan during 1978–1979 are presented. From 8 species seven are recorded for Kyrgyzstan and one from Kazakhstan for the first time.

Key words: Diptera, Dolichopodidae, fauna, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan.

Негробов О.П. и Гричанов И.Я. Новые данные о Dolichopodidae (Diptera) из Казахстана и Киргизии. Резюме. Представлены результаты сборов долихоподид (8 видов) в различных районах Казахстана и Киргизии в 1978–1979 гг. Для семи видов впервые публикуется материал из Киргизии и для одного вида — из Казахстана.

Ключевые слова: Diptera, Dolichopodidae, фауна, Казахстан, Киргизия.

Негробов О.П. і Гричанов І.Я. Нові відомості про Dolichopodidae (Diptera) з Казахстану і Киргизії. Резюме. Наведено результати зборів доліхоподид (8 видів) у різних районах Казахстану і Киргизії у 1978–1979 рр. Для семи видів уперше опубліковано матеріал з Киргизії і для одного виду — з Казахстану.

Ключові слова: Diptera, Dolichopodidae, фауна, Казахстан, Киргизія.

Introduction

The first data on dolichopodid species from the Middle Asia and Kazakhstan were inserted in the Catalogue of the family Dolichopodidae (Diptera) of the Soviet Union (Гричанов, Негробов, 1979). Negrobov (1991) included several previously unpublished finds of species in the Catalogue of Palaearctic Diptera, however giving no original collection records.

Material and Methods

All the material was collected by sweeping with a net in several localities in Kyrgyzstan and southern Kazakhstan observed by Igor Grichanov during 1978–1979 expeditions (collector's name is omitted in the list below). Detailed collection data have never been published. Some key characters for selected species are here illustrated. Specimens examined in this study are deposited in the collection of the Voronezh State University (VSU). General distribution of species is given after Negrobov (1991) and Grichanov (2003–2010).

New records

Dolichopus asiaticus Negrobov, 1973

Material examined. Kyrgyzstan: E Isyk-Kol, Mikhailovka env. 15.07.1979, 1♂.

Distribution. Mongolia, E Russia: Buryatia, Ukraine: Kherson. Type locality: Russia: “Burjatskaja ASSR Flußtal Ustj-Barguzin, Jarechta, Wiese”.

Dolichopus campestris Meigen, 1824 (Figs. 1–2)

Material examined. Kazakhstan: N Tian Shan, Alma-Atinskii Reserve, Pravyi Talgar Riv., 1600 m, 13.07.1978, 2♂; Kazakhstan: N Tian Shan, Alma-Atinskii Reserve, Srednii Talgar riv. gorge, 28.07.1979, 3♂; Kyrgyzstan: Rybachye [Balykchi] env., 4.07.1979, 2♂.

Distribution. Algeria, Armenia, Austria, Belarus, Belgium, Czech, Denmark, Egypt, Estonia, Finland, France, Georgia, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Latvia, Lithuania, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania; N Russia: Karelia, Leningrad, Novgorod; S Russia: Alania, Kabardino-Balkaria, Krasnodar; E Russia: Altai, Kamchatka, Khabarovsk and Primorskii Terr.; Slova-

nia, Sweden, Switzerland, UK; Ukraine: Carpathian Mountains, Odessa. Type locality: not given.

Figs. 1–2. *Dolichopus campestris* Meigen: 1 — antenna; 2 — cercus.

Dolichopus nubilus Meigen, 1824 (Figs. 3–4)

Material examined. Kyrgyzstan: Isyk-Kol Lake, Ananyevo, 1600 m, 20.08.1978, 8 ♂; Kyrgyzstan: Sary-Chelek Nature Reserve, Arkit, 1200 m, 28.06.1978, 2 ♂.

Distribution. Armenia, Austria, Azerbaijan, Belgium, Bulgaria, China (Xinjiang), Czech, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece incl. Crete; Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Latvia, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, N Russia: Karelia, Leningrad; S Russia: Adygea, Krasnodar, Rostov; Slovakia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Tajikistan, Ukraine: Kherson, Odessa; UK, Uzbekistan. Type locality: not given.

Figs. 3–4. *Dolichopus nubilus* Meigen: 3 — antenna, 4 — hypopygium.

Dolichopus oxianus Stackelberg, 1930

Material examined. Kyrgyzstan: Isyk-Kol Lake, Chon-Örүktü, 10–11.07.1979, 2 ♂; Kyrgyzstan: Isyk-Kol Lake, Ottuk, 21.07.1979, 3 ♂.

Distribution. Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, Tajikistan. Type locality: “Turkestan: Iskander-Kul, Gultsha, Oburden, Tshiburgan, Fan, Alai”.

Dolichopus perversus Loew, 1871 (Figs. 5–6)

Material examined. Kyrgyzstan: Sary-Chelek Nature Reserve, 1200m, 2.07.1978, 2 ♂.

Distribution. Armenia, Israel, Turkey, Tajikistan, N Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan. Type locality: Tajikistan: “Sarawschan Thal, Turkestan” [= Zeravshan valley].

Figs. 5–6. *Dolichopus perversus* Loew: 5 — wing, 6 — hypopygium.

Rhaphium discigerum Stenhammar, 1850 (Figs. 7–8)

Material examined. Kyrgyzstan: E Isyk-Kol Lake, Mikhailovka env., Dzhergalan Riv. valley, 16.07.1979, 1 ♂.

Distribution. Austria, Belgium, Czech, France, Germany, Hungary, Kyrgyzstan, Romania, N Russia: Pskov; S Russia: Krasnodar; Sweden, Ukraine: Crimea. Type locality: Sweden: “Haradshammar, Ostergothland”.

Figs. 7–8. *Rhaphium discigerum* Stenhammar: 7 — habitus, 8 — wing.

Rhaphium laticorne (Fallén, 1823) (Figs. 9–10)

Material examined: Kyrgyzstan: Isyk-Kol Lake, Ananyevo, 1600 m, 17.08.1978, 6.07.1979, 4 ♂; Kyrgyzstan: Isyk-Kol Lake, Mikhailovka env., Dzhergalan Riv. valley, 14.07.1979, 13 ♂; Kyrgyzstan: Isyk-Kol Lake, Tyup env., Tyup Riv. shore, 16.07.1979, 4 ♂.

Distribution. Austria, Armenia, Belarus, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, N Russia: Leningrad, Murmansk, Pskov; M Russia: Voronezh, Lipetsk;

Figs. 9–10. *Rhaphium laticorne* (Fallén): 9 — habitus, 10 — wing.

S Russia: Krasnodar; E Russia: Altai; Krasnoyarsk territory, Slovakia, Sweden, UK, Ukraine, Turkey, Yugoslavia. Type locality: Sweden.

Syntormon turanicus Stackelberg, 1927

Material examined. Kazakhstan: N Tian Shan, Alma-Atinskii Reserve, Pravyyi Talgar Riv., 1600 m, 9.08.1978, 1 ♂.

Distribution. Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan. Type locality (holotype): “Turkestan: Chanatum Kokand, montes Alaiensis, prope amniculum Kizil-su”.

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